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Environmental Modulation of Retinal Excited States in Schizorhodopsin-4: A State-Specific QM/MM Study in an Explicit Membrane

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Schizorhodopsins are a recently identified family of microbial rhodopsins that, in contrast to canonical Type I, exhibit inward proton pumping function. Here, we investigate the photophysics of Schizorhodopsin-4 using microsecond molecular dynamics of the full trimer embedded in an explicit double-leaflet membrane, combined with high-level QM/MM excited-state simulations, including polarization and dispersion effects. The ground-state dynamics reveal a distinct preorganization of the retinal binding pocket, characterized by a strongly stabilized retinal protonated Schiff base-counterion interaction and a dynamically hydrated intracellular aspartic acid. Vertical excitation energies computed at the XMS-CASPT2 and TD-DFT levels quantitatively reproduce the experimental absorption maximum. Analysis of environmental fluctuations using spectral density formalism shows that protein-chromophore dynamics dominate inhomogeneous broadening of the absorption band. These results point out a ground-state electrostatic and hydration asymmetry of the chromophore pocket that is markedly different from that of canonical outward proton-pumping rhodopsins and is consistent with inward proton pumping.

1 Introduction

The photochemical behavior of rhodopsins is crucial for light-driven biological signaling, providing a powerful tool for optogenetic engineering.^{1–9} Rhodopsins are photoreceptive membrane proteins and are classified as Type I (animal) or Type II (microbial) according to the initial configuration of the retinal protonated Schiff base (rPSB) within the binding pocket (i.e. 11-*cis* in animals and all-*trans* in microbes). Accordingly, their primary photoisomerization follows opposite pathways: 11-*cis* → all-*trans* in animal rhodopsins and all-*trans* → 13-*cis* in microbial rhodopsins.^{10–13} The structural features of the binding pocket are tightly coupled to both the trajectory and the timescale of photoisomerization reactions.¹⁴

A new subfamily of microbial rhodopsins, the retinal-binding light-activated Schizorhodopsins (SzRs), was recently discovered in Asgard archaea by Bulzu *et al.*^{15,16} Crystal structure of Schizorhodopsin-4 (SzR4), later determined by Higuchi *et al.* and deposited under PDB ID 7E4G, was resolved at 2.1 Å by X-ray diffraction only very recently.¹⁷ Unlike classical bacteriorhodopsins (BhRs), which pump protons outward, SzR4 functions as an inward H⁺ pump, thereby reversing the canonical direction of transport.^{5,18} Its structural organization and spectroscopic properties, distinct from those of other rhodopsin families including BhRs and heliorhodopsins (HeRs),^{6,19} point to alterna-

tive photochemical mechanisms underlying its activity.^{17,20,21}

First analysis of the SzR4 crystal structure provides first qualitative hints into the molecular environment and chemical interactions that govern its photochemical behavior, including color tuning and photocycle kinetics, by mainly inspection of the (uncommon) binding pocket composition. Specific interactions, such as those involving D184, as the primary proton acceptor, regulate protonation equilibria and electronic responses, thereby shaping the absorption spectra.^{5,17,22,23} Residues in direct contact with the polyene chain (conjugate π -system) further tune the S₀ → S_x transitions.^{17,22} Experimental characterization revealed a pronounced absorption maximum of the bright-state at 2.22 eV (\approx 550 nm), attributed to retinal singlet excitations in the Franck-Condon (FC) region,¹⁷ pointing out also a strong pH-dependency: increasing pH reduces the intensity of the main band, induces a slight blue shift, and alters proton-transfer pathways central to the SzR photocycle.^{17,21}

Beyond a static description, it is essential to consider how the hydrated membrane-protein environment dynamically²⁴ modulates the photophysics of wild-type SzR4. The chromophore in its dark-adapted state continuously exchanges perturbations with the protein scaffold, the surrounding lipids, and both internal and bulk waters. Several key questions remain open: how hydration develops and reorganizes inside the binding pocket; how

internal waters reshape the local hydrogen-bond network; how transient lipid contacts influence the chromophore's microenvironment; and to what extent environmental fluctuations modulate mutual polarization and the response of the low-lying excited states. These dynamical effects ultimately may shape the vibronic structure, contribute to the asymmetry of the absorption bands, and may influence the earliest steps of the photocycle. To address these points, we examine SzR4 electronic transitions using electrostatic and polarizable embedding schemes that explicitly incorporate the time-dependent electrostatic landscape generated by the protein–membrane–water assembly.

A stepwise protocol combining extensive state-of-the-art all-atom classical Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations with a hybrid quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) framework was employed. Multi-configurational calculations at the Extended Multi-state Complete Active Space Second-order Perturbation Theory (XMS-CASPT2) level of theory are used to benchmark excitation energies of dark-state rPSB. We also tested Time-Dependent Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) simulation in order to include also polarizable environment response and dispersion interactions at QM/MM level by using the QM/MMpol-cLR³ approach.²⁵, not available at the XMS-CASPT2 level of theory at the moment. This integrative methodology enables a dynamic atomistic resolution of SzR4 absorption spectra, provides mechanistic insight into its photoisomerization, and establishes a foundation for probing and engineering rhodopsin-based photoreceptors with tailored optogenetic properties.

2 Methodology

2.1 System Setup

The initial model for the classical molecular dynamics (MM MD) simulations was derived from the atomic-resolution X-ray structure of wild-type Schizorhodopsin-4 (SzR4) in its homotrimeric form, deposited in the Protein Data Bank under PDB code 7E4G.¹⁷ To generate a structurally symmetric assembly, the protomer with the highest local resolution was chosen as the template. In contrast, the remaining two protomers were reconstructed by comparative homology modelling using the MODELLER^{26–28} package, ensuring sequence and structural conservation across all (seven) transmembrane helices. Unresolved regions, such as external loops absent from the experimental structure, were not modeled and capped with the corresponding NME and ACE groups, while missing heavy atoms were rebuilt during the homology procedure. The resulting homotrimeric assembly was adopted as the starting point for all subsequent simulations.

Protonation states of ionizable residues were assigned using PROPKA^{29,30} (v. 3.2), based on pK_a predictions obtained with the Amber ff14SB³¹ force field at pH 8. The retinal protonated Schiff base (rPSB), covalently linked to Lys188 (Fig. 1), was explicitly included in this procedure to preserve the experimentally relevant protonation environment.

Distinct lipid bilayer compositions were employed to model the monomeric and trimeric states of SzR4 in environments closely resembling their physiological membrane context. The monomer was embedded in a mixed bilayer of neutral POPE (1-palmitoyl-2-

oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine) and anionic POPG (1-palmitoyl-2-oleoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoglycerol) at a 3 : 1 molar ratio, consistent with experimental membrane conditions.¹⁷ In contrast, the trimer was inserted into a homogeneous POPE bilayer, reflecting the predominance of this lipid species in native biological membranes. POPE lipid has the interesting characteristic of performing several hydrogen bonds via the ammonium group with the system component and acting as the donor.³²

Initial explicit membrane–protein assemblies were generated with PACKMOL–Memgen³³, and final optimization and explicit solvation were performed with PACKMOL^{34,35}, ensuring full hydration of the protein surface and lipid headgroups. For the trimeric system, a specific refinement was applied: four POPE molecules were manually placed within the central pore to prevent nonphysical permeation of water and ions, thereby preserving the structural and functional integrity of the membrane–protein interface. The number of lipids introduced was estimated by approximating the pore as a cylinder with the maximum radius that avoids steric clashes with adjacent side chains. The final count of inserted POPE molecules was obtained by comparing the pore volume with the molecular volume of a single POPE lipid, ensuring realistic packing without overlap.

Electrostatic neutrality was achieved by adding the appropriate counter-ions, and sodium and chloride ions (NaCl) were included to reach a physiological salt concentration of 0.15 M using the tleap module from AmberTools23.³⁶ The final solvated trimeric system comprised 135,170 atoms in a periodic boundary condition (PBC) box of $10.93 \times 10.92 \times 11.39$ nm³, whereas the monomeric system comprised 57,775 atoms. In all cases, the z-axis was aligned with the normal vector of the membrane plane. The final simulation setup is depicted in Fig. 1.

2.2 Classical Molecular Dynamics Simulations

All-atom molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of the wild-type (WT) system were carried out using a systematic, multi-step equilibration protocol designed to eliminate steric clashes and ensure system stability before the production phase dynamics. The protocol commenced with an energy minimization step, in which harmonic positional restraints (force constant of 100 kJ·mol⁻¹·nm⁻²) were applied to the protein backbone, the chromophore, and lipid atoms. Energy minimization was performed for up to 100,000 steps or until the maximum force on any atom fell below 0.001 kJ·mol⁻¹·nm⁻¹.

Subsequently, a five-stage temperature annealing procedure was performed using the velocity-rescale (V-rescale) thermostat, gradually increasing the system temperature through discrete steps of 50, 120, 180, 250, and 310 K. This was followed by equilibration in two stages: a 500 ps simulation in the canonical (NVT) ensemble, and five successive 500 ps simulations in the isothermal–isobaric (NPT) ensemble, resulting in a total equilibration time of 3 ns. Positional restraints applied to the protein backbone and chromophore atoms were progressively reduced during the equilibration phase, ranging from 100 to 0.1 kcal·mol⁻¹·Å⁻², and were fully removed before the production run. No restraints were applied to the lipid atoms at any equilibration stage. All equili-

functional in combination with the 6-31G* basis set.^{53,54} All QM/MM calculations were performed using a combination of the Amber24⁵⁵ (Sander) molecular mechanics engine and the Gaussian 16 package for the electronic structure calculations.⁵⁶

2.4 Classical Electrostatic Effects

The contributions of the complex environment, particularly the interaction between the binding pocket and the rPSB photoreceptor and its influence on the electronic transitions of the chromophore, were investigated by comparing the multiscale QM/MM approach with gas-phase reference calculations.

A long-time scale configurational sampling of rPSB geometries was extracted from the all-atom classical MD trajectory of the hydrated membrane-protein system. In the gas-phase reference, the chromophore was isolated by removing the embedding from each snapshot and capping with a hydrogen atom the valency of the QM atoms that are located in the covalent bond across the QM/MM boundary frontier, thereby providing a baseline description free from environmental effects (but thermally equilibrated). In parallel, the same snapshots (initial conditions, IC) were evaluated within a hybrid quantum mechanics/molecular mechanics (QM/MM) framework, explicitly incorporating electrostatic contributions from the surrounding hydrated protein-lipid matrix (FF static point charges).

The QM/MM boundary at the C δ -C γ single bond was treated using Morokuma's hydrogen link-atom (HLA) scheme.⁵² To prevent over-polarization within the QM region, the charges of atoms located near the boundary (C ϵ , C δ , H δ , and the N-H group of K188, see Fig. 1) were set to zero, and the residual charge was redistributed among the remaining MM atoms of the same residue LYR188, rPSB. Two QM regions were considered for single-point calculations: (i) the minimal one, which includes the rPSB (Fig. 1), and (ii) an extended one that also comprises the counter-ion side chain of residue D184, following the crystal structure numbering.

Vertical excitation energies (ΔE) and transition property (oscillator strengths, f) were carried out with the Extended Multi-State Complete Active-Space Second-Order Perturbation Theory (XMS-CASPT2)⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹ using reference wavefunctions from the State-Averaged Complete Active Space Self-Consistent Field (SA-CASSCF) method⁶⁰ and Time Depend Density Functional Theory (TD-DFT) with the hybrid functional M062X.

The active space comprised all π and π^* orbitals of the chromophore, corresponding to 12 active electrons in 12 active orbitals, consistent with previous reports.⁶ To ensure the reproducibility of the present study, the complete π -active space of the rPSB is provided in the Supplementary Information (Fig. S??). This active space is sufficiently flexible to describe the lowest-lying electronic transition characters.

An imaginary shift⁶¹ of 0.2 a.u. was applied to mitigate intruder-state problems, and no ionization potential-electron affinity (IPEA)⁶² correction was employed. Reference electronic wavefunctions were obtained with the SA(3)-CASSCF(12, 12) procedure, averaging over the ground state and two excited states (S_1 and S_2). All multi-reference calculations were performed with

OpenMolcas (v. 24),^{63,64} interfaced with the Tinker MM software (v. 6.3.3).⁶⁵

All electronic-structure energy calculations were conducted without periodic boundary conditions (PBC) and employing the 6-31G* atomic basis set.^{66,67} Since the electronic structure codes do not employ PBC, the system dimension was reduced by carving out the simulation cell to retain only molecules within a radius of 30 Å of the rPSB center, thereby retaining electrostatic contributions while reducing computational cost.

Representative conformations were extracted from 100 ns time interval of the all-atom MD production trajectory (500 – 600 ns time interval). A total of 500 ICs for each monomer were sampled at regular 200 ps intervals (1500 single-points calculations). Preparation of the ICs was performed using GROMACS topology and coordinate files, which were subsequently converted into Tinker⁶⁵ and Gaussian 16 input formats.

The final lineshape of the simulated absorption-vibronic spectrum of SzR4 was obtained by convoluting vertical excitation energies and oscillator strengths with Gaussian functions as lineshape envelopes in the explicit heterogeneous condensed phase by Nuclear Ensemble Approach (see SI).

2.5 Spectral Density Approach, Polarizable and Quantum Effects

To rationalize the spectroscopy of the SzR4 in condensed-phase and recover the asymmetry observed in the main absorption band of the rPSB, we employed a Spectral Density (SD) formalism using a ground-state BOMD. This system-bath approach allows for the disentanglement of both homogeneous and inhomogeneous contributions to the spectral line shape by explicitly accounting (cumulant framework) for the dynamical coupling between electronic transitions and the vibrational modes of the surrounding matrix through the Autocorrelation function (ACF) of the vertical excitation energies (excitation energy fluctuations).⁶⁸

The computational protocol adopted for constructing the SD spectra follows well-established methodologies previously applied to photoactive and light-harvesting systems.⁶⁸⁻⁷² Because the SD approach is computationally demanding—requiring a very large number of electronic structure calculations within a QM/MMpol framework—the excitation energies were computed at linear-response TD-DFT(M062X/6-31G*) level of theory.

Environmental effects, e.g., the specific architecture of the protein cavity, were treated by explicitly considering the mutual polarization between the chromophore and its surroundings through polarizable-embedding QM/MMpol excited-state calculations.⁷³ In this setup, an inner shell of 10 Å around the rPSB was described as polarizable sites, whereas fixed atomic multipoles represented the outer region (10 – 15 Å).

The final excitation energies were computed, encompassing state-specific corrections to recover, in an affordable manner, both polarization response and dispersion contributions, ensuring an accurate description of excited states at the TD-DFT level in the presence of a responsive environment. To this end, we used here the recently developed QM/MMpol-cLR³ model,²⁵ implemented in a development version of the Gaussian suite of pro-

grams.⁵⁶ A total of 4000 QM/MMpol-cLR³ single-point excitation state energies were performed for S_1 excited state. In addition to 10000 electronic structure calculations at QM/MMpol-cLR^{2,74} level, splitted in S_1 and S_2 excited states. The snapshots were extracted every 5 fs of the GS BOMD equilibration.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Protein Structural Dynamics

To explore the dynamical properties and stability of the newly discovered SzR4 inward-pumping channel, MD simulations of both the trimeric and monomeric forms were performed. The detailed setup and production protocol is described in the Methods section.

Fig. 2 A: Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) of backbone atom positions over the simulated timescale. B: per-residue Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) for the three monomers (monomer 1, M1, red; monomer 2, M2, blue; monomer 3, M3, green). The seven transmembrane helix sections are highlighted in gray with labels indicating the numbering. Selected Intra/Extracellular loops are also labeled.

In the following, we report only the results and discussion concerning the trimer, which is expected to represent the functional form of SzR4. Accordingly, all spectral property calculations were carried out on structures sampled from the trimer simulation. Nevertheless, a comparison with the structural properties obtained from the monomer simulations is provided in the Supporting Information (SI), to offer a basis for understanding the effects of modeling rhodopsins as monomers when they are natively multimeric. Overall, comparison between the trimer and monomer simulations reveals shared structural motifs, but crucial interactions in the retinal cavity and motions at both terminal regions of the proton channel are influenced by the loss of trimeric hindrance control (see SI section for detailed comparison).

In order to assess the stability of the MD simulation, several analyses were performed. In the first place, membrane structural parameters were monitored throughout the simulation to verify bilayer equilibration. Specifically, the Area per Lipid (APL) and the Membrane Thickness (MB, computed as the average distance between the phosphorus atoms of the two leaflets) are shown in Fig. S1A and S1B, respectively. The APL converges to 0.71 nm² within approximately 150 ns. The bilayer thickness remains stable from the early stages of the simulation, reaching an average value of 4.14 nm after an induction period of \approx 100 ns.

The stability of the protein was assessed starting from the Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) of the backbone over time, reported in Fig. 2A. The RMSD of the full trimer rapidly reaches a first plateau after a few tens of nanoseconds, followed by a second stabilization around 400 ns. This behavior suggests that the time evolution of the RMSD is influenced by both the initial structural relaxation and slower functional conformational motions. In addition, distinct behaviors emerge when considering the individual monomers. In particular, monomers M1 and M2 reach a stable RMSD value before 100 ns, whereas M3 still displays noticeable fluctuations within the same timescale (Fig. S2A).

To discriminate between the equilibration phase and the native fluctuations associated with intrinsic protein flexibility, as well as to account for the different behavior of the three monomers, the RMSD Autocorrelation function (RMSD-ACF) was calculated for each monomer over the entire trajectory (Fig. S2B). The RMSD-ACF was fitted to a bi-exponential expression containing an exponentially damped oscillatory term, revealing a primary decay of RMSD fluctuations on a timescale of a 10 – 20 ns for M1 and M2, and up to 100 ns for M3. After this initial decay, corresponding to the initial structural relaxation, M2 exhibits an essentially flat profile. On the contrary, M1 and M3 exhibit an oscillatory behavior in their RMSD-ACF, suggesting the occurrence of reversible conformational motions. Based on the above results, the initial structural relaxation time was estimated to be approximately 200 ns (details of the RMSD-ACF fitting that motivated this choice are provided in the SI).

To gain insights into the conformational motions, the backbone Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) and the RMSD per-residue were computed for each monomer. The RMSF profiles are shown in Fig. 2B, while the per-residue RMSD values are reported in Fig. S3B. The RMSF highlights the amplitude of residue fluctuations around their average positions, whereas the per-residue RMSD quantifies deviations relative to the initial structure. Both analyses identify the same flexible regions of the protein sequence, mainly corresponding to loop segments connecting the transmembrane (TM) helices and, overall, the three monomers exhibit comparable flexibility profiles. Following the nomenclature commonly used for rhodopsins, loops are named according to the membrane side they face - intracellular (ICL) or extracellular (ECL) - and numbered sequentially from 1 to 3.⁷⁵ The first highly mobile loop connects TM1 and TM2 on the intracellular side (ICL1). The second, between TM2 and TM3, is a long loop facing the extracellular environment (ECL1). Among the other loops, only ICL3 (between TM5 and TM6) displays comparable flexibility. Interestingly, M2 exhibits lower flexibility for

both ECL1 and ICL3 compared to M1 and M3. The per-residue RMSD provides complementary information: despite the reduced flexibility of ICL1 and ICL3 in M2, their RMSD values are comparable to those of M1 and M3. This suggests that M2 is generally more rigid, yet undergoes structural rearrangements similar in magnitude to those of the other monomers relative to the crystal structure. Conversely, the RMSD of ECL1 in M2 remains lower, indicating that this region is not only stiffer but also more similar to the crystallographic counterpart.

The role of the long extracellular loop in the activation of rhodopsins^{76–78}, and more generally within the broader G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) family, is well established. It is worth noting that in microbial rhodopsins, the long extracellular loop corresponds to ECL1, whereas in animal rhodopsins and other GPCRs connects TM4 and TM5, this is identified as ECL2. Despite this topological difference, the structural role and functional implications of this loop appear to be conserved. For instance, in bovine rhodopsin, ECL2 forms a rigid β -sheet lid over the chromophore-binding pocket and interacts with the protein core through a disulfide bond and several hydrophobic contacts. Disruption of this loop impairs proper folding and hinders the formation of the active state, indicating that ECL2 mechanically drives conformational rearrangements upon activation. Across the GPCR family, ECL2 contributes to ligand recognition, acts as a gating element for the binding pocket, and modulates receptor activation.^{75,79,80} In SzR4, ECL1 exhibits a high degree of flexibility, and its motion relative to the protein is governed exclusively by non-covalent interactions.

To further investigate the loop motions identified by the RMSF and RMSD analyses, a principal component analysis (PCA), also referred to as essential dynamics (ED)⁸¹, was performed on the C_α atomic coordinates along the MM MD trajectory. In order to analyze the collective motions occurring within a single monomer, the ED analysis was performed on the covariance matrix calculated from the trajectories obtained by concatenating the individual monomer trajectories. The analysis yielded that the two dominant eigenvectors (ev) correspond primarily to motions of ECL1 and ICL3 and, to a lesser extent, ECL3, ICL1 and ILC2 (Fig. S4). In what follows, the motions localized at the extra- and intra-cellular sides will be discussed separately.

3.1.1 Structural dynamics at the Extracellular Side

Fig. 3A shows the two extreme conformations associated with the first (and largest) eigenvector, focusing on the extracellular side. It can be clearly observed that, along this collective motion, ECL1 undergoes a large displacement, transitioning from a conformation positioned over the extracellular entrance of the SzR4 channel to a fully shifted state that exposes the terminal portion of the channel cavity to bulk water. Therefore, ECL1 acts as a “lid” the sliding of which results in an easier access of water molecules within the cavity at the extracellular end of the channel. This cavity will hereafter be referred to as the extracellular cavity (ECC), in line with the EC loops nomenclature. To describe the ECL1 sliding motion we identified as structural descriptor the C_α - C_α distance between T58 (Threonine-58) and N172 (Asparagine-172) (see Fig. 3A in which the C_α atoms of these residues are shown as

green spheres). Since T58 is located near the middle of ECL1 and N172 lies at the beginning of helix TM7, their distance well defines the open and closed state of the ECC. As shown in Fig. 3B, the distribution of this distance exhibits in fact a clear bimodal pattern corresponding to the two ECC states, the population of which can be estimated using a cut-off distance corresponding to the minimum in the bimodal distribution (1.25 nm). According to this definition, the ECC closed state is slightly more sampled than the closed one (0.52 vs 0.48, respectively). Additionally, in Fig. S5A, the time evolution of the same distances is reported. Here, M2 and M3 show some open-closed transitions in the first half of the MM MD, then remain mostly closed. Otherwise, M1 stays mostly open, but shows several transitions over the entire MM MD trajectory. Since the lid opening allows access of water to the EC cavity, we examined the number of water molecules inside the ECC in both the closed and open state (see the SI for details on the cavity definition). The water count distribution within the ECC was found to be bimodal and similar in shape to the T58-N172 distance distribution (Fig. S5B in the SI). In addition, as shown in Fig. 3C, the number of water molecules well correlates with the T58-N172 distance (Correlation Coefficient of 0.79), confirming that the displacement of the lid indeed increases the water content within the protein.

Two main basins can be identified in Fig. 3C: the first corresponds to the closed-lid state, characterized by an average T58-N172 distance of approximately 1.1 nm and an average of about 21 water molecules within the EC cavity. The second, centered around a distance of 1.4 nm between the two key residues, corresponds to the open-lid state, with roughly 32 water molecules in the cavity. Further increases in the inter-residue distance do not lead to a proportional rise in water count. This is evidenced by the yellow region in the density plot shifting mainly upward, indicating that the cavity is already essentially fully hydrated at a T58-N172 distance of approximately 1.4 nm. Possibly, this open/closed dynamics, if retained also in the further steps of the photocycle, could heavily affect the water and proton relocation in the proton-pump functioning of SzR4.

3.1.2 Structural Dynamics at the Intracellular Side

Another crucial step in the photocycle is the proton release toward the intracellular medium, in which the motions occurring on the intracellular side of the protein, particularly within the intracellular cavity (IC), are expected to play a key role. ED analysis shows that the main contributions to the first two eigenvectors at the IC side arise from the relative motions of loops ICL2 and ICL3 (Fig. S4).

Similarly to the extracellular loops, also the intracellular ones have been connected to structural stabilization and activation roles.^{75,82} In particular, in ICL2, the mutation of few conserved residues over different families of GPCR protein, showed impairing of the protein functionality.⁷⁵ In Fig. 4A, the top view of the extreme configurations along the first eigenvector (ev1) is reported. It can be observed that the relative position of ICL2 and ICL3 is modulated by the formation/rupture of a salt bridge (SB) between Arginine-87 (R87) and Glutamate-142 (E142) and an hydrogen bond (HB) between R140 and the C=O group in

Fig. 3 A: Structural representation of the two extreme configurations corresponding to the first eigenvector obtained from ED analysis (extracellular side). Water molecules within the protein interior are shown as red spheres. The C_{α} atoms of the residues defining the movement of the extracellular loop 2 ("lid") and their inter-residue distance are shown as green spheres and dashed lines, respectively. B: Normalized distribution of the C_{α} - C_{α} distance between T58 and N172. The dashed gray line marks the 1.25 nm threshold that discriminates between the open and closed states of the extracellular cavity. The populations of the closed and open states are also reported. C: Correlation between the T58-N172 distance and the number of water molecules inside the ECC cavity, shown as a density plot where dark colors indicate higher sampling and light colors indicate lower sampling. The regression line and its correlation coefficient are shown in red.

the backbone of R87 (see Fig. S6A and B for distance distribution). This last HB is supported by the electrostatic interaction between Aspartate-89 (D89) and R140. In particular, the distance describing the R87 HB with the backbone of R140 displays a strong correlation (0.76) with the projection of the trajectory on ev1 (see Fig. S6D). Throughout the MM MD trajectory, the formation of these SB and HB is not synchronous and all four formed/broken state combinations are sampled. The R87-E142 salt bridge is formed for approximately for half of the simulation (Fig. S6B). When not interacting with E142, R87 can also engage in a π - π stacking interaction with the nearby Tyrosine-84 (Y84) (see Fig. S6C). Notably, the behavior of Y84 appears to be related to changes in the accessibility of the intracellular cavity that connects to the proton-release channel. In particular, the mobility and interaction pattern of Y84 modulate the solvent exposure of E81, a residue previously suggested to act as the final proton acceptor before release into the bulk solvent.¹⁷

A previous work showed that E81 is easily solvent exposed, being shielded from bulk water only by two leucine residues, L30 and L85.¹⁷ In agreement with this observation, L30 and L80 do not display significant motions in the present simulations and do not affect E81 solvent exposure. Instead, the simulation shows that Y84 can tune the water accessibility to E81. The Y84 side chain is highly mobile and capable of interacting with several nearby residues, including R87 (on ICL2), E81 (on TM3), and Lysine-29 (K29) (on ICL1). As qualitatively shown in Fig. 4A, the Y84-K29 contact transiently shields E81 from the solvent. To quantify this effect, the solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) of E81 was calculated over the MM MD trajectory. The average SASA is 0.19 nm², with large fluctuations over time. When configurations are separated based on the presence of the Y84-K29 interaction (defined as occurring at distances below 0.43 nm, i.e., the minimum of the Y84-K29 distance distribution shown in Fig. S7A), a clear difference emerges. The average SASA of E81 is 0.12 nm² when the Y84-K29 interaction is formed, and increases to 0.23 nm² when it is absent (see Fig. S7B). This observation

indicates that the Y84-K29 interaction may modulate the effectiveness of E81 in proton shuttling.

It is worth noting that the E81 configuration observed in the crystal structure, stabilized by two hydrogen bonds with Asparagine-34 (N34) and Threonine-195 (T195) in TM2 and TM7, respectively, is not preserved for most of the simulation time. Instead, during the MD trajectory, the E81 side chain rotates toward the protein external side and either forms a salt bridge with K29 or is hydrogen bonded to water (see Fig. S8C for the distance distributions and representative structures). The higher stability of the E81-K29 SB compared with the E81-N34/T195 hydrogen bonds is consistent with the solvent-exposed and negatively charged nature of E81, which favors interactions with nearby charged residues or water molecules over hydrogen bonding within a hydrophobic environment. This salt bridge also helps stabilizing the deprotonated state of E81, consistent with experimental observations indicating that E81 remains deprotonated throughout the photocycle.¹⁶ A similar interaction pattern was proposed for another member of the Schizorhodopsin family, namely AntR.¹⁷ The final proton acceptor in AntR is suggested to be D30, which is solvent exposed and hydrogen-bonded to R84 and Y193, i.e., with an interaction pattern similar to that observed in our MD simulations with E81 and K29 mimicking the roles of D30 and R84 in AntR.

3.1.3 Reaction Pocket Stability

Going into more detail on the fine structural features, we focused on the stability of the retinal chromophore reaction pocket. An extensive analysis of the relevant salt bridges and hydrogen bonds in the first and second-shell environments of the retinal protonated Schiff-base (rPSB) was performed.

The retinal counterion, Aspartate-184 (D184), forms a strong and persistent interaction with the protonated nitrogen of the retinal across all three monomers, with a O(D184)-N(rPSB) distance distribution peaked at 2.75 Å (see Fig. S9A). This distance is shorter than that observed in the X-ray structure (3.02-3.11 Å),

Fig. 4 A: Structural representation of the two extreme configurations corresponding to the first eigenvector obtained from ED analysis (intracellular side). The intracellular loops ICL2 and ICL3 are highlighted in orange, and the four residues R87, D89, R140 and E142, involved in salt bridges/hydrogen bonds are shown as sticks. B: Representative structures showing the two possible conformations of K29 and Y84 that modulate E81 solvent exposure. The protein is shown as surface and color palette indicates the positive and negative residues (in blue and red, respectively), the hydrophilic and hydrophobic residues (in green and white, respectively).

but is consistent with the strong retinal-counterion interactions reported in other rhodopsins, both in classical MD studies⁸³ and in QM/MD simulations.⁸⁴

In addition, D184 forms two HBs with nearby Tyrosine residues, namely Y45 and Y71, both located along the channel and considered key components of the proton transport chain.¹⁷ A detailed representation of the main interactions surrounding the retinal and D184 is shown in Fig. 5C&D. Both the Y71–D184 and the Y45–D184 interactions remains strong and stable throughout the MM MD trajectory in all three monomers, with a sharp O–O distance distribution peaked at 2.75 Å. In the X-ray structure, D184 also interacts with a nearby charged residue, R67, through a water-mediated contact with a heavy-atom distance of 3.51–3.59 Å. This interaction has been proposed to play a crucial role in tuning the pK_a of D184 and preventing its protonation.¹⁷ The MM MD sampling reveals that R67 adopts three main configurations with respect to D184 (Fig. 5A): R67 can interact with D184 either *via* a direct (42%) or *via* a water-mediated (26%) SB. Alternatively, R67 can be completely disengaged from the cluster of interactions surrounding the retinal counterion (32%). When R67 completely loses contact with D184, it becomes fully solvated within the extracellular cavity (ECC) at the top of the channel.

Fig. 5 A: normalized distribution of the minimum distance between R67 and D184 sidechains heavyatoms. B: Normalized distribution of the number of water molecules inside the retinal pocket in the two basins with closed (pomace) and open (orange) R67–D184 salt bridge gate. Selected water molecules are within 12 Å of the R67 (C_ζ) carbon and simultaneously within 9 Å from the rPSB nitrogen. C and D: structural representation of the two states of the R67–D184 gate, that highlights the main interactions of the retinal counterion and the different number of water molecules in the vicinity of the retinal chromophore.

The tilting motion of the R67 side chain (see Fig. 5C&D for a graphical representation) can transiently connect the immediate surroundings of the retinal with the terminal portion of the ECC. This movement of R67 has been proposed to play a key role after retinal isomerization, facilitating water, and consequently proton, access to the deprotonated retinal, thereby contributing to the recovery of the dark-state.^{16,17} However, the present MM MD simulations suggest that a dual-basin configuration of R67 interactions, capable of modulating the hydration level of the reaction pocket, can also occur before isomerization.

The hypothesis that R67 may act as a gating element for water access to the reaction cavity is further supported by the observation that changes in the Arginine side-chain orientation modulate the hydration of the immediate vicinity of the retinal Schiff base. In particular, when the D184–R67 interaction is lost, the gate opens and, if the lid is open and the ECC cavity is hydrated, water molecules can penetrate the pocket. To quantify this effect, the number of water molecules in the retinal pocket was calculated for the subset of structures in which the ECL1 lid is open. The waters in the retinal cavity are defined as those within 12 Å of the R67 (C_ζ) carbon and simultaneously within 9 Å from the rPSB nitrogen. Water population histograms and representative structures are shown in Fig. 5B, C&D. The analysis reveals that when R67 is in close contact with the retinal, only a few water molecules (typically three or fewer) are confined within the pocket. These water molecules are also present in the crystallographic structure. Conversely, when the gate is open, four to five

Fig. 6 Lipid-protein interactions along the entire all-atom MD, expanded to 1.1 μ s. Analysis carried out taking into account a dual cutoff (0.45-0.70 nm).

water molecules are usually present. This variation in water content appears small but is however, significant within such a confined space and, most importantly, provides evidence that when the D184-R67 gate is open, water can enter and exit the retinal cavity with relevant fallout on the proton recovery kinetics in the latest steps of the photocycle.

3.2 Lipid-Protein Interaction Dynamics

Lipid-protein interactions may influence the conformational equilibrium of membrane proteins and, ultimately, their biological function.⁸⁵ To characterize how POPE lipids (neutral) interact dynamically with SzR4 at atomic resolution, we first ensured that the membrane reached a stable equilibration regime (see Protein Structural Dynamics section). Building on this equilibrated state, we examined lipid-protein interactions across all residues by analyzing several dynamical descriptors of the lipid conformational phase space (Fig. 6). In particular, the residence time (RT) of bound POPE molecules, e.g., reflecting non-diffusive, persistent interactions, was obtained from the survival-time Autocorrelation function as implemented in the PyLipID framework.⁵¹

Fig. 6 shows a clear pattern of lipid interactions across the protein surface. Notably, most protein residues form medium- to short-lived contacts with nearby lipids, with residence times of less than 500 ns. Highlighting that our spectroscopic properties (sampled from 500 to 600 ns) were carried out on a well-equilibrated hydrated membrane protein. More long-term interactions were observed across the MD simulation and corresponded mostly to the interval of residues indexed from 300 to

Fig. 7 Representative side and top views of the most common (cluster analysis) POPE-binding sites (sphere representation), identified using a dual-cutoff scheme and requiring at least four interacting protein residues per site. The SzR4 homotrimer is shown in white, the retinal chromophore in yellow, and the bound POPE molecules in gray.

400. The residues G366, K317, and A365 showed the longest average interaction durations, corresponding to the entire simulation time. Concerning the quantification of the surrounding lipid number to complement the Residence time analysis, we found that the maximum number is approximately 5.79 near residue I358 (Fig. 6).

The lipid-count analysis (Fig. 6) also shows that the protein surface remains consistently surrounded by POPE molecules, with most residues maintaining at least one lipid in proximity throughout the MM MD trajectory. This behavior is consistent with a well-equilibrated membrane environment, highlighting the heterogeneous nature of the homotrimer surface. Furthermore, the repeating pattern observed along the residue index reflects the structural symmetry of the three protomers, as expected for a homotrimer embedded in a uniform lipid bilayer. The binding sites were detected automatically by pyLIPID routines (Fig. 7). It is noteworthy that each binding site is composed of at least 4 SzR4 residues.

As shown in Fig. 7, the lipids located within the central pore of the homotrimer display remarkable stability, indicating that this region constitutes a functionally relevant binding site that likely contributes to the structural integrity of the membrane protein. Among the external lipid-binding areas, the site adjacent to the chromophore's β -ionone ring is particularly relevant because it places the POPE apolar tail close to the retinal environment, e.g. binding pocket. The kinetic analysis shows, however, that this contact is short-lived at the residue level: for the position equivalent to rPSB(188), individual events last only 15.1 ± 24.6 ns, yielding a residue-level residence time of 44.5 ns and a comparatively fast dissociation rate ($k_{\text{off}} = 0.022 - 0.113 \text{ ns}^{-1}$, $R^2 = 0.9987$). The low lipid count at this residue (~ 1.03) further supports the notion of brief, superficial encounters. Importantly, this behavior does not reflect the stability of the binding site as a whole: the site remains continuously populated (100% occupancy, Fig. 6), accommodates more lipids on average (24.1), and exhibits a much longer site-level residence time (277 ns) together with slower dissociation ($k_{\text{off}} = 0.004 \text{ ns}^{-1}$). Thus, while residue rPSB188 interacts only transiently, the surrounding environment forms a stable region of lipid-binding throughout the simulation.

Fig. 8 Experimental absorption spectrum of SzR4 (highest-resolution protomer) compared with simulated spectra from MM-MD-sampled geometries. Mechanical Ensemble (ME) spectra were obtained from gas-phase QM calculations, whereas Electrostatic Embedding (EE) includes the membrane-protein electrostatic field via fixed MM point charges in a QM/MM framework. (A) XMS(3)-CASPT2(12,12)/6-31G*. (B) Linear-response TD-DFT at the M062X/6-31G* level, using either an rPSB-only QM region or an extended QM region including the D184 side chain. All spectra employ Gaussian broadening ($\sigma = 0.10$ eV). Absorption maxima are given in the legend and referenced to S_1 . Line shapes were generated using the Nuclear Ensemble Approach (see Supporting Information). Experimental data reproduced from ref.¹⁷.

3.3 Modulation of Spectral Tuning in SzR4

Simulating the absorption spectra associated with the early photochemical steps of the rPSB photocycle, particularly the nature, energetics, and relative ordering of the low-lying singlet excited states, remains challenging.^{86,87} In heterogeneous biological environments, non-covalent interactions beyond pure electrostatics act cooperatively to modulate excitation energies, oscillator strengths and vibrations, thereby determining the overall spectral line shape.^{71,88} Fig. 8 displays the SzR4 absorption spectra obtained using different computational strategies at the line shape carried out using the NEA strategy, highlighting systematic shifts as conformational sampling and environmental effects are progressively incorporated.

To establish a baseline, excitation energies were initially obtained on both the crystallographic structure (PDB 7E4G)¹⁷ and QM-optimized geometries in the gas phase (isolated). At the reference geometry (crystallographic) linear-response TD-DFT/M062X predicts a blue shift of 0.14 eV relative to experiment, which exhibits a dominant absorption band centered approximately at 2.22 eV.¹⁷ XMS-CASPT2 with the full π -active space shows a larger deviation of -0.26 eV. Upon geometry optimization at each level of theory, both methods display an additional blue shift of comparable magnitude relative to the obtained on top of crystallographic geometry. These results indicate that discrepancies with experiment are not governed solely by the electronic-structure approximation, but are also strongly influenced by the underlying rPSB geometry.

Structural deviations with respect to the crystallographic structure are primarily localized at the C ϵ atom of K188. In the absence of protein-induced constraints, C ϵ relaxes from a C ϵ -N-C15-C14 dihedral of -145.99° in the crystal to 179.98° (M062X) and 179.90° (XMS-CASPT2), whereas the C ϵ -N-C15 bond angle remains essentially unchanged (Fig. X, SI). The nearly identical

dihedral values indicate that M062X and XMS-CASPT2 predict highly consistent relaxation along this coordinate. Although this relaxation leads to a more planar chromophore, the Bond-Length Alternation (BLA), defined here as $\langle r_{\text{single}} \rangle - \langle r_{\text{double}} \rangle$, increases from 0.0060 Å in the crystallographic structure to 0.0100 and 0.0104 Å at the XMS-CASPT2 and M062X levels, respectively, indicating enhanced single-double bond alternation and reduced effective π -conjugation in the absence of the protein electrostatic field. This increase in BLA directly rationalizes the blue shift observed in the gas-phase optimized rPSB geometry.⁸⁹

Representative chromophore conformations were incorporated by computing gas-phase absorption spectra including thermal effects over an ensemble of 500 force-field geometries extracted every 0.2 ns from the 100 ns production segment of the MM MD trajectory, using a mechanical embedding (ME) scheme (Fig. 8, blue curves). In the ME calculations, the electronic Hamiltonian contains no explicit environmental contributions, such that only geometrical disorder inherited from the MM trajectory is retained. Relative to single optimized-structure calculations, explicit conformational sampling induces a pronounced red shift of the absorption maximum ($\hbar\nu$). At the XMS-CASPT2 level, $\hbar\nu$ shifts from 2.12 to 1.98 eV ($\Delta E = -0.14$ eV), while TD-DFT/M062X exhibits a comparable shift from 2.48 to 2.29 eV ($\Delta E = -0.19$ eV).⁸

Although single- and multireference approaches yield different absolute excitation energies, both methods qualitatively agree on the effect of thermal sampling, predicting similar red shifts and analogous variations of the lowest excited state across the ensemble. The convergence of the S_1 and S_2 excitation energies with respect to ensemble size is reported in Figs. S14 and S15.

Inclusion of the hydrated membrane-protein environment through standard QM/MM electrostatic embedding (EE) introduces the opposite effect (Fig. 8, red curves). Within this framework, the chromophore experiences the static electrostatic poten-

tial generated by the explicit lipid bilayer, solvent, and protein, represented by fixed MM point charges. At the TD-DFT level of theory, the MM environment polarizes the ground-state electronic density⁹⁰, whereas in XMS-CASPT2 it acts on the state-averaged density; excited state-specific electronic relaxation is neglected in both approaches.

Relative to the ME ensemble, the nonpolarizable model induces systematic blue shifts of 0.12 eV at the XMS-CASPT2 level and 0.04 eV at TD-DFT/M062X. This effect reflects preferential stabilization of the ground-state density by the surrounding membrane–protein matrix, primarily mediated by electrostatic interactions between the positively charged rPSB and its primary counterion D184, in agreement with previous studies on bovine rhodopsin.^{89,91}

Across both ME and EE, TD-DFT/M062X reproduces the photophysics behavior observed at the XMS-CASPT2 level within the Franck–Condon region (rPSB dark state), capturing the red shift induced by thermal sampling and the blue shift introduced by electrostatic embedding. Although absolute excitation energies differ between single- and multireference treatments, these trends are consistently reproduced. On this basis, TD-DFT/M062X was adopted as the electronic-structure level for subsequent analyses, owing to its favorable cost–accuracy balance, while acknowledging the known limitations of TD-DFT in describing excited-state dipole moments.⁹² Similar blue-shift trends are observed for the S_2 state, accompanied by changes in relative oscillator strength.

To assess the robustness of the adopted computational protocol, additional tests were performed addressing QM region expansion, protomer variability, and basis-set effects. Inclusion of the D184 side chain in the QM region at the TD-DFT level leads to a modest additional shift of 0.04 eV relative to the minimal model, indicating increased sensitivity of the chromophore to its immediate electrostatic environment. Potential subunit-dependent effects were evaluated through TD-DFT/M062X single-point calculations for each SzR4 protomer (A, B, and C), totaling 1,500 excitation energies under a fixed point-charge model with the expanded QM region (Fig. S20). The resulting excitation-energy distributions are essentially identical across the three protomers, yielding an average peak position of 2.40 eV, consistent with Fig. 8 and confirming the structural equivalence of the binding pockets. Finally, basis-set effects were evaluated by comparing 6-31G* and 6-31+G* on a frame-by-frame basis, revealing variations of 0.02–0.05 eV in the low-lying excitation energies despite a substantial increase in computational cost (Fig. S19). Taken together, these results indicate that the simulated absorption features are only weakly affected by QM region expansion beyond the primary counterion, protomer identity, and diffuse basis functions, supporting the consistency of the adopted computational protocol.

3.4 Responsive Environment and Nonclassical Effects

Electrostatic embedding represents the simplest QM/MM framework for incorporating environmental electrostatics and rationalizing photo-induced processes in rhodopsins. However, mutual polarization and dispersion effects, as well as their state-specific

contributions to excitation energies, are neglected. These nonclassical interactions can alter both ground- and excited-state energetics and thereby modulate the spectral tuning and line shape.²⁵

Fig. 9 illustrates the stepwise inclusion of polarization and dispersion contributions through an atomistic, state-specific QM/MMpol treatment, incorporating atomic charges and induced dipoles to describe the coupling between the rPSB chromophore and fluctuations of the SzR4 binding pocket, evaluated over the same ensemble used in Fig. 8. Given the distinct functional properties of SzR4 relative to other microbial rhodopsins, as discussed above, this system provides a suitable platform for assessing the role of responsive environmental effects in modulating chromophore photophysics.

Fig. 9 Calculated absorption spectra of SzR4 at the ω_0 , cLR, cLR², and cLR³ protocols compared with experiment. All theoretical spectra were generated using the Nuclear Ensemble Approach with Gaussian broadening ($\sigma = 0.10$ eV), based on 500 rPSB geometries sampled from classical MM MD. The corresponding absorption maxima are reported in the legend.

In the cLR³ model, the effective excitation-energy is decomposed as:²⁵

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{\text{cLR}^3} &= \Delta E_{\text{cLR}^2} + R_{\text{SS-disp}} \\ &= \Delta E_{\text{cLR}} + R_{\text{LR-disp}} + R_{\text{SS-disp}} \\ &= \Delta E_{\text{GS-pol}} + R_{\text{SS-pol}} + R_{\text{LR-disp}} + R_{\text{SS-disp}}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta E_{\text{GS-pol}}$ denotes that the polarization effects is kept frozen at S_0 density of the chromophore (hereafter referred to as ω_0), $R_{\text{SS-pol}}$ accounts for state-specific-induced environment polarization (cLR)⁹³, $R_{\text{LR-disp}}$ represents dispersion correction evaluated within linear response taking into account the response of the chromophore to the environment fluctuations (cLR²), and $R_{\text{SS-disp}}$ captures state-specific dispersion corrections (cLR³).

Inclusion of ground-state polarization (equilibrium) at the QM/MMpol- ω_0 level induces a hypsochromic shift of approximately 0.11 eV relative to the respective optimized geometry (2.48 eV, Fig. 8). This behavior reflects preferential stabilization of the ground state by the protein environment and is consistent

with the persistent hydrogen bond observed between the rPSB chromophore and the negatively charged D184 residue along the MM trajectory.⁸⁹

Explicit inclusion of state-specific polarization (cLR), arising from the response of excited-state densities (SS-pol), partially compensates this effect, converting the initial blue shift into a red shift of approximately -0.05 eV for both S_1 and S_2 states, thereby highlighting the excited-state density reorganization. This contribution modifies the direction of spectral shift, but indicates that induced polarization effects alone do not dominate spectral tuning under the present conditions.

Linear-response dispersion contributions (LR-disp) within the cLR² scheme induce a modest red shift of -0.14 eV, which is observed relative to the initial QM/MMpol- ω_0 predictions. This stabilization is given from the response of the rPSB photoexcitation to environmental fluctuations through dispersion, partially compensating the blue shift induced by ground-state polarization and counterion quenching.⁸⁹ An additional contribution stems from the electronic nature of the first excited state, which is predicted to be less polar than the ground state due to its charge-transfer character. Consistent with previous model studies, the QM/MMPol-cLR² approach therefore provides an efficient description of CT states, leading to improved agreement with experiment.⁷⁴

State-specific dispersion contributions, defined as the difference between excited- and ground-state dispersion energies, arise from correlated electronic density fluctuations between the rPSB chromophore and its surrounding environment and capture a complementary nonclassical component of the chromophore-protein interaction. In the present case, the dominant corrections up to the cLR² level can be rationalized in terms of two successive molecular-environment mechanisms (Eq. 1), which are predicted to red-shift the excitation energies.^{94,95} The QM/MMpol-cLR² approach reflects the environment's response to chromophore electronic fluctuations, accounting for an additional correction associated with environment-chromophore electronic coupling. By contrast, the subsequent state-specific dispersion term included at the QM/MMpol-cLR³ level produces only a small additional effect.

Since the ground-state reference energy remains unchanged across all corrected linear-response schemes, the residual shift must originate from de-stabilization of the excited state, indicating an electronic contribution to the spectral tuning. In this context, the SzR4 binding pocket can be described as a low-dielectric, heterogeneous environment—comparable to a nonpolar medium with an effective dielectric constant in the range $\epsilon \approx 2-4$ ⁹⁶ for which nonclassical dispersion and response effects contribute in a quantitatively moderate manner.

It is worth emphasizing that the QM/MMpol-cLR³ (Eq. 1) correction cannot be interpreted straightforwardly in a simple additive scheme, as it depends on the difference between the molecular polarizability in both electronic states.^{25,94} Within this framework, the successive spectral shifts can be rationalized in terms of distinct contributions, summarized schematically as:

$$\omega_0 \xrightarrow{-\Delta_1} \text{cLR} \xrightarrow{-\Delta_2} \text{cLR}^2 \xrightarrow{\pm\Delta_3} \text{cLR}^3 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 10 Simulated vibronic spectra of SzR4 (protomer with the highest crystallographic resolution)¹⁷ compared with the experimental spectrum. Spectra were generated from SD of excitation-energy fluctuations using S_1 and S_2 energies computed at the M062X/6-31G* level within QM/MMpol from ground-state QM/MM BOMD ensembles. QM/MMpol- $(\omega_0, \text{cLR}, \text{cLR}^2)$ curves are based on five spectral-density calculations, whereas QM/MMPol-cLR³ is based on four (S_1 only). Each spectrum includes 1000 excited-state energy evaluations; absorption maximum ($h\nu$) are indicated in the legend.

The key concept underlying the cLR² $\xrightarrow{\pm\Delta_3}$ cLR³ shift correction is the molecular polarizability, α_{mol} , evaluated for different electronic states (S_0 and S_x , $x = 1, 2$). Within this picture, the trivial blue shift (0.01 eV) observed upon inclusion of the environmental response can be rationalized by a larger ground-state polarizability relative to the first excited state, $\alpha_{\text{mol}}^{S_0} > \alpha_{\text{mol}}^{S_1}$, leading to preferential stabilization of S_0 . By contrast, the S_2 state follows the opposite trend, consistent with its different electronic degree of freedom redistribution pattern. The reported values are obtained from sampling over 100 ns of MM MD trajectory, accounting exclusively for static disorder effects.

Non-negligible vibronic effects associated with dynamic disorder were analyzed using SD, $J(\omega)$, obtained from excitation-energy fluctuations along ground-state QM/MM BOMD trajectories, and are displayed in Fig. 10. The spectral density was constructed from the Fourier transform of the energy-gap ACF and directly reflects how nuclear motion modulates the electronic excitation. Ground-state anharmonicities are included via QM/MM sampling, while gap fluctuations are treated within a second-order cumulant expansion. Static disorder is further sampled by averaging the vibronic spectra over four/five independent trajectories. Although higher-order couplings and explicit excited-state gradient effects are neglected, this combined treatment provides a consistent description of line-shape broadening in the heterogeneous environment as SzR4.

The trends observed for the relative stabilization of the electronic states and the factors determining the absorption maximum of SzR4 are consistent between the NEA results and the vibronic spectra obtained from spectral density calculations (Fig. 10). Nevertheless, the QM/MMpol-cLR³ spectral density results exhibit an additional red shift relative to NEA. This difference likely reflects limited configurational sampling and the

intrinsically higher sensitivity of state-specific dispersion (local environment) to ensemble fluctuations compared to polarization and linear-response contributions. This behavior is further supported by the molecular polarizability distributions of the S_0 and S_1 states (Fig. 11). While the ground-state polarizability spans approximately 400–600 a.u. and remains largely symmetric, the excited-state distribution is markedly asymmetric, with a long tail extending to ~ 1200 a.u. Considering the relation $\alpha_{\text{mol}}^{S_1} - \alpha_{\text{mol}}^{S_0} > 0$, the central regions of these distributions would predict a purely red-shifted contribution within the SzR4 binding pocket. However, the pronounced asymmetry of the excited-state polarizability indicates that state-specific dispersion can also introduce competing blue-shift components arising from less frequent but highly polarizable configurations, highlighting an intrinsically electronic source of spectral modulation.

Regarding the comparison with experiment, a small shift in the absorption maximum is observed and may be rationalized by the TD-DFT level limitations, as an underestimate of the differential polarization contribution. In addition, we demonstrate that the pronounced asymmetry of the experimental band originates from the combined effects of homogeneous and inhomogeneous broadening, the latter lying beyond the scope of the NEA framework. Nevertheless, upon inclusion of electrostatic embedding, electronic response effects, and intrinsic broadening mechanisms captured through the combination of QM/MMpol-cLR³ approach and spectral density formalism are responsible for the modulation of the final simulated absorption line shape.

Fig. 11 Distribution of the molecular polarizability of rPSB embedded in the SzR4 binding pocket. The molecular polarizability was computed as the sum of the atomic contributions to the z-component of the molecular polarizability tensor over 4000 snapshots extracted from the QM/MM BOMD trajectory.

4 Conclusion

The recently characterized SzR4 rhodopsin is investigated at the atomistic level to establish how protein–membrane organization, thermal fluctuations, and chromophore electronic response interplay in a non-trivial manner to determine the absorption spectrum. By combining classical MM MD, QM/MM Born–Oppenheimer trajectories, and polarizable QM/MMpol-

cLR³ effective excitation energies, we quantify spectral tuning, disentangle homogeneous and inhomogeneous broadening contributions to the line shape, and compute the vibronic absorption spectrum under thermal conditions.

Classical MD captures the dominant fluctuations in the geometry and electrostatic organization of the binding pocket arising from rearrangements of hydrogen-bond and salt-bridge networks involving the retinal chromophore and key surrounding residues, together with variations in local hydration and protein–lipid contacts. These collective structural and electrostatic fluctuations modulate the local electric field acting on the chromophore and generate the configurational heterogeneity responsible for inhomogeneous spectral broadening. QM/MM Born–Oppenheimer dynamics, in turn, resolves fast intramolecular degrees of freedom of rPSB that contribute predominantly to homogeneous broadening.

The electronic analysis shows that spectral tuning cannot be rationalized by electrostatics alone. State-specific polarization and dispersion contributions jointly define an effective excitation energy, and their balance is system-dependent, leading to a non-trivial interpretation of spectral shifts. Within QM/MMPol-cLR³, the cLR³ term explicitly captures the mutual state-specific electronic response between chromophore and environment (chromophore→environment and environment→chromophore), rather than a one-way embedding correction. Mechanistically, this mutual response couples the instantaneous pocket configuration to fluctuations in chromophore polarizability, yielding a systematic additional red shift relative to QM/MMPol-cLR² and clarifying why dispersion-driven effects track ensemble variability while preserving the relative peak positions.

Overall, SzR4 exemplifies that a quantitative and interpretable description of rhodopsin photophysics requires treating, in the same atomistic polarizable setting, (i) pocket-level structural/electrostatic fluctuations that control inhomogeneous broadening, (ii) chromophore intramolecular dynamics that governs homogeneous and vibronic contributions, and (iii) state-specific polarization and dispersion, including their mutual chromophore–environment response. The key outcome is therefore not only agreement with experiment, but a mechanistic decomposition of how protein–membrane fluctuations and state-specific electronic effects together set the effective excitation energy and the observed absorption line shape.

Author contributions

All authors conceived the research. CAG and CC developed the methodology. CAG, CC and LC performed the simulations. CAG and CC analyzed the results. All authors wrote the manuscript.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Data availability

A data availability statement (DAS) is required to be submitted alongside all articles. Please read our full guidance on data availability statements for more details and examples of suitable statements you can use.

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